

ORION | Trapezium

A Monthly Publication of the ORION Astronomical Society

Lunar Eclipse
March 2024
Knoxville, TN

© Noah Frere

This page shows a loop of lunar images from the total lunar eclipse of 14 Mar 2025, captured by ORION member Noah Frere using a 250mm Canon t3 at his residence in South Knoxville, Tennessee. Here, time progresses counterclockwise.

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Page Three Astronomy

*It's a Gorn, my lord, in a Flatbed Ford
Slowin' down to take a look at me*

The **ORION Astronomical Society** is a science and astronomy group founded in April 1974 by scientists from the United States Department of Energy facilities at Oak Ridge, Tennessee. We primarily serve the communities of Oak Ridge and Knoxville and the counties of Anderson, Knox, and Roane.

ORION's mission is to support scientific research, teaching, and astronomical activities in East Tennessee. We hold monthly public meetings at the Oak Ridge RSCC Campus, and are active at Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO), hosting public events, sharing knowledge of the skies, and helping to provide intellectually stimulating programs. ORION works to share the wonders of the cosmos and the culture of science.

ORION members include scientists, engineers, technicians, IT experts, artists, students, and others with varied talents and expertise. Over half of ORION members own telescopes, many are amateur radio operators, and some have expertise in astrophotography.

ORION has working relationships with several organizations, including museums and other amateur astronomy groups. Membership is open to individuals who will actively contribute their time and ideas. The annual membership fee is \$20, and student discounts are available. There is no charge for our newsletters and publications, or for participation in most ORION activities.

ORION Board and Officers:

President: Don Spong

VP and Program Chair: David Fields

Social Chair: Noah Frere

Secretary: Rob Fowler

Treasurer: Bob Edwards

Editor quondam: Ted Barnes

Astrotechnologist: Rob Scott

Videographer: Rob Fowler

Obed Site Outreach: Joshua Gray.

TRAPEZIUM is a monthly publication of the ORION Astronomical Society. The issue date is the Friday preceding the monthly ORION meeting, chosen to provide timely information regarding the planned Program.

From March 2025 we will be issuing a shorter version of the Trapezium, which will still include important information regarding the monthly ORION presentation, as well as dates and other information regarding Public Stargazes and other notable events relating to ORION and TAO.

We expect to go through several iterations of this shorter Trapezium; we have already concluded that some components, such as a separate Astrophotography section, are so important for a publication on amateur astronomy that one really cannot justify excluding them.

Messages from ORION

Orionites, as we move into June we begin the transition from galaxy season to Milky Way season. Both provide plenty of interesting objects to view and image. Unfortunately, rainy/cloudy weather persists in East Tennessee and limits our opportunities for observation. During these cloudy times, I've gotten interested in reading about some recent developments in the search for extraterrestrial intelligence. A recent news item in livescience.com ([LiveScienceStarPulses](http://livescience.com)) "Strange' star pulses detected in search for extraterrestrial intelligence" got me started and describes work by an advanced amateur astronomer, Richard Stanton, who has done photometric measurements over many years of changes in light coming from 1,300 sun-like stars. This has recently been published in *Acta Astronautica* (see: [Stanton](#)) and discusses several anomalous light pulses that he cannot explain based on known phenomena. He models the waveforms of the pulses as arising from light diffraction around an object with sharp edges and concludes the object may be within our solar system. This reinforces an earlier paper ([CambridgeUniv](#)) that suggests our best chances of finding evidence of extraterrestrial intelligence may lie within our own solar system. Finally, there is an inspiring 2012 TED talk by SETI researcher Seth Shostak ([SETI](#)) that discusses the issues involved and concludes contact is increasingly likely. So hold onto your hats and keep an eye out for signs of ET! If you have trouble accessing these papers, I have the pdfs and can send them to you.

For June the new moon will be June 25th and both the weekends of June 21-22 and 28-29 should be good dark sky weekends. The full moon is on June 11th and is known as the Strawberry Moon; it will have a low position in the sky and is one the lowest full moons we'll have for some time. There are no meteor showers in June, and the planets are pretty much out of view, except for early morning. Mars is visible in the evening, but not in a very good position. Deep sky objects of interest include: M106 at 24 Mly (million light years) in Canis Venatici; M51 (Whirlpool galaxy) at 31 Mly in Canis Venatici; NGC 4565 (a famous edge-on spiral galaxy) at 39 Mly in Coma Berenices; M82/M81 (spiral galaxies) at 12 Mly in Ursa Major; M57 (Ring Nebula) at 2500 ly in Lyra, and the M92 and M13 globular star clusters at 27,000 and 22,000 ly in Hercules. For M13 it's a good test of your optics if you can identify the "propeller" structure near the center of the cluster.

Hyperlinks:

LiveScienceStarPulses = https://www.livescience.com/space/extraterrestrial-life/strange-star-pulses-detected-in-search-for-extraterrestrial-intelligence?utm_term=FB2B349C-F7DD-4FE2-ACC0-5438B2499109&lrh=d161150667e1255973d6e3bb58139138bba990126431070e7cf90b595e4b9740&utm_campaign=368B3745-DDE0-4A69-A2E8-62503D85375D&utm_medium=email&utm_content=82A82C4E-1AFF-4E01-8AAD-8CF95E8B18CB&utm_source=SmartBrief

Stanton = <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0094576525002449#bib15>

CambridgeUniv = <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/symposium-international-astronomical-union/article/searching-for-extraterrestrial-technologies-within-our-solar-system/873208CF339B2E6E944C7FF379ED2B83>

SETI = https://www.ted.com/talks/seth_shostak_et_is_probably_out_there_get_ready

Observatory Way

June 2025

The photo on the left shows our new road sign for the Roane State Tamke Allan Observatory. Traveling west, the sign is on the left as you turn into Observatory Way from Caney Creek Road, just past Joiner Hollow Road.

TAO Public Stargazes and Special Events

TAO offers stargazes to the community on the 1st and 3rd Saturdays of each month, weather permitting. Our usual schedule for the summer is to open at 8:30 pm and continue to nominally 10:30 pm -- later when the sky and attendance encourage this. Opening time changes according to the season, and a good guide is to arrive at the observatory about sunset, when weather is encouraging. These stargazes are supported by local astronomy clubs, especially ORION members and friends, and benefit our students and community. Our TAO stargazes are usually well-attended, with a full classroom of visitors for evening astronomy lectures.

TAO Astronomers support our Astronomy Classes, our Public Stargazes, and our Special Events. Examples of special events are eclipses, planetary transits across the sun, and Asteroid Occultations. A recurring special event is our monthly "International Friendship Stargaze" which is held during the week of the first quarter moon at the Bissell Park "International Friendship Bell" in Oak Ridge".

Many of our events are highly successful, but we avoid inclement and dangerous weather conditions. Working around the weather challenges of East Tennessee proves interesting.

May 17 TAO Stargaze

Everyone was very comfortable – it was a pleasant evening, with almost no mosquitoes. Skies were not the best since we had a summer haze, and the evening moon was brighter than we might like. It's better not to complain though. Images from this event are shown on the following page.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Setup began at sunset for this truly enjoyable stargaze. Here's an aerial photo from astronomer/drone pilot Don Spong showing some of the early arrivals.

Thanks to Ted Barnes for the photos below. See also pp.28-31 and p.62 for additional photos of this enjoyable event.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

June International Friendship Stargaze

Each month we offer a first quarter moon urban stargaze in the spirit of International Friendship. We had an excellent evening on June 1, attended by astronomers Art, Don, David, Kevin, Rob and Sunny the Astrodog. Our honored bell striker of our June International Friendship Stargaze was Evie Gibson.

An article about this stargaze appears on pp.32-34 of the Trapezium.

New Oak Ridge Library Displays

ORION and TAO Astronomers are completing work on the Oak Ridge library displays. The first accents some of the adventures offered by astronomy as one follows challenges and progress over a wide span of human history.

The display offers several historically important astronomy books, a small telescope (excellent for beginners), an "Eggclipse" hand-painted Astronomy Egg that commemorates the 2024 total solar eclipse; an early barometer; and some other astronomical and calculating instruments.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

This second library display focuses more on photographic challenges and discoveries, and what amateur astronomers may find in the skies.

Other offerings in display #2 are a second small (reflecting) telescope; an ORION 50th anniversary T-Shirt that also commemorates our recent solar eclipse; and some solar filters that were designed by local astronomers, assembled by our TAO astronomy students, and given to participants at our TAO planetary occultation observations.

The displays were assembled by ORION astronomers, a few of whom are shown here in the hall of the library that contains the displays:

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

ORION Astronomy Society Oak Ridge Library Exhibit 2 Assembly Team.
L to R, David Fields, Don Spong, Rob Fowler and Juan Carbajo.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Astrospheric PRO Status now available for ORION and TAO astronomers

Over the past 5 years most astronomers have appreciated the usefulness of Astrospheric (www dot astrospheric dot com). The program is now available on our TAO website www dot roanestate dot edu / obs) and as free apps for Android and iPhone devices. For those astronomers wanting personalized access to Astrospheric, ORION has recently achieved Pro membership for the group, and makes Pro membership in Astrospheric available to TAO astronomers. Anyone wishing to avail themselves of this opportunity can follow these instructions:

Register with Astrospheric for a free account. I use the iPhone app and usually login to www dot astrospheric dot com .

Next, from the **Astrospheric** home page on an iPhone, Android, or browser, do this:

- + ensure you're logged into your Astrospheric account
- + click the little sparkling **S** at the upper right of the screen to enter the Subspace section;
- + select JOIN GROUP and select Oak Ridge Isochronous Observation Network (ORION);
- then
- + request membership.

When your request is processed, you'll become a PRO member of Astrospheric.

TAO Director’s Message (cont.)

Comparison of Astrospheric and Clear Sky Chart Predictions

Some astronomers use both Astrospheric and Clear Sky Chart (CSC) to predict good skies for astronomy. In general CSC provides more detailed meteorological data than Astrospheric, whereas Astrospheric offers astronomical tools that go beyond cloud predictions.

The challenge in making cloud cover predictions is to offer useful predictions that are both long-range and frequently updated. Predictions of cloud cover for times farther into the future is discussed on the Clear Sky Chart website:

“The line labeled **Cloud Cover** forecasts total cloud cover. The colors are picked from what color the sky is likely to be, with Dark blue being clear. Lighter shades of blue are increasing cloudiness and white is overcast. This forecast may miss low cloud and afternoon thunderstorms. When the forecast is clear, the sky may still be hazy, if the transparency forecast is poor.

Accuracy averaged over North America for a 30 day period: when the forecast is predicting less than 12 hours into the future, mostly-clear forecasts (cloud<25%) have been right 80% of the time. Mostly-cloudy forecasts (cloud>75%) have been right 91% of the time. When the forecast is predicting 36 to 48 hours into the future, the mostly-clear accuracy is 76% and the mostly-cloudy accuracy is 89%. Accuracy beyond 48 hours in unknown.”

[www dot cleardarksky dot com / RoaneStObkey dot html](http://www.dotcleardarksky.com/RoaneStObkey.html)

Clear Sky Clock documents very well the importance of frequently updating the forecasts. From information on these cloud prediction websites, our options are as follows:

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

- (1) We can rely on the Clear Sky Clock staff to provide updates each 12 hours.
- (2) We can rely on the Astrospheric Staff to provide prediction updates each 6 hours for their basic (free) membership.
- (3) We can rely on the Astrospheric staff to provide prediction updates each hour for "Pro" users.

The more frequent updates of Astrospheric Pro suggest that it is likely the best choice for accurate cloud cover information.

TAO Director's Message (cont.)

Supporting Tamke-Allan Observatory

Amateur astronomers are always welcome to join ORION and participate in activities at TAO. Many people visit TAO, join in our activities, share their knowledge and telescopes, and even provide refreshments for our ever appreciative visitors and staff.

The history of the Observatory shows the importance of donations, which may be made through the Roane State Foundation or www.doe.roanestate.edu/?5871-Roane-State-Foundation.

The Observatory continues to be supported by the college. Its growth and functionality is augmented by contributions of time and energy by the local amateur astronomy community, especially the ORION Astronomical Society (<http://orioninc.org>), and by donations of funds and equipment. Notable contributions include the donation of a large-aperture telescope by Dr. Roy Morrow, in memory of his grandson; the donation of a professional-quality telescope and supporting funds by Margaret Morrow, in memory of Roy and his love for astronomy; and the donation of supporting funds by Dr. William Marshall, in memory of his wife Joanne Marshall and local astronomer Mary Watson. These have all helped make the Tamke-Allan Observatory a valuable and widely appreciated community resource.

ORION Board Meetings

- Rob Fowler

This is a summary of topics discussed recently at the weekly (Monday 1 pm) ORION Board Meeting held as a regular working lunch at ElCantarito restaurant in Oak Ridge. Notes as contributed in Stardate format by Sec. Rob Fowler.

Stardate 2025.03.31

In attendance were Robert Fowler, Ted Barnes, David Fields, Art Alison and Don Spong.
Discussed delays on new dome report due to committee participant availability.
Discussed possible going to TAO Tuesday night.
Discussed next speaker is not firm for April's meeting.
Discussed voting for officers at the next ORION Meeting.
Discussed the next Friendship Stargaze and date for same, 8th possibly.
Discussed possibly coming up with cloudy night entertainment for Friendship stargaze.
Discussed Wordsworth poem about telescopes.
Discussed potential security cams for TAO.

Stardate 2025.04.07

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes and Rob Fowler
Ted discussed the data acquired from his Arduino/LED test
David discussed a mount having the ability to track asteroids via PHD2
David discussed the Friendship Stargaze is 7:30pm Tuesday
Discussed needing pics of new concrete pads at TAO

Stardate 2025.04.14

In attendance were David, Ted, Art and Rob.
Ted discussed results of the Zwetana #785 occultation. After a long and dramatic story, Ted revealed a successful capture.
Noah is reaching out to Joe Baldwin about next month's presentation.
Ted discussed quantum field theory using functional methods.

Stardate: 2025.04.21

In attendance were David Fields, Ted barnes, Art Alison, Noah Frere and Rob Fowler
Ted discused how to use AnyDesk and log in unattended
Ted Discussed a planetary occultation, Mars vs a 9th magnitude star on May 6th at 1 am.
David discussed progress he is making with a Meshtastic receiver

ORION Board Meetings (cont.)

- Rob Fowler

Stardate: 2025.04.21 (cont.)

Mentioned 4 visitors who showed up at TAO and new member Kevin Wilson

David brought up calendar access

Discussed problem with rotation of glow dome lid. Watch for migration of wheel axels.

One axle migrated in and caused the lid to bind.

Stardate: 2025.04.28

In attendance were David Fields, Ted Barnes, Art Alison, Kevin Wilson, John Cliff and Rob Fowler

Briefly mentioned domes on CloudyNights.com

Discussed Upcoming Mars/Star occultation and relevant challenges.

HD 74058 vs Mars just after midnight 00:44 night 5th/6th morn.

TAO Stargaze beginning at May 3rd 8pm

Friendship Stargaze Possibly May 6th

Briefly discussed avoiding Feynman's van

Shared astrophotos

Discussed potentially going to TAO tonight & Noah's class

Stardate: 2025.05.05

In attendance were David Fields, Art Alison, Ted Barnes, Kevin Wilson, and Rob Fowler

David asked if we have a set program for May. That remains unclear. Ted contacted Noah to confirm. We await a reply.

Ted mentioned the next annual IOTA meeting is possibly going to be in New Mexico in Oct.

Stardate: 2025.05.12

At 11am David, Ted & Art met at the Library and made a first pass at setting up a display case for the club. Rob joined later. It was artistically done, decorated with a small telescope, some antique books, and astrophotos.

Discussed whether Kevin might give the May lecture and what topics he has ready. He agreed to speak on the topic of stellar spectroscopy. Ted mentioned the next possible occultation on the early morning on 5/21/2025.

Stardate: 2025.05.19

In attendance were Don, David, Ted, Art, Kevin, and Rob

Kevin brought up Benjamin Baniker as a potential lecturer.

Rob announced that the most recent lecture is on YouTube.

ORION Monthly Meeting

ORION Monthly Meeting Format

Meeting Venue: City Room (A-111), just inside the main entrance, Coffey/McNalley Bldg., Oak Ridge Campus, Roane State Community College.

7:00 pm Eastern, 3rd Wednesday of each month.

Our monthly meetings (except for December, a dinner) generally proceed as follows:

- Welcome
- Announcements
- Invited Presentation and Discussion
- Awarding of the Mug
- Astrophotography / Special Presentations

The nominal start time is 7:00 pm Eastern, on the 3rd Wednesday of the month. The beginning of the meeting will usually include announcements of general interest.

Meetings typically continue until around 9:00 pm. Please plan to stay until the end. Hopefully we will all enjoy the astrophotography and other special topics discussed in the latter part of the meeting.

Remote Viewing: A live Zoom session will usually be open during the ORION Monthly Meeting, at the link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/88528735960?pwd=KzY4bnBHcjlhTzg3L3pOcjY0TFovUT09> or
<https://bit.ly/42apGxX>

Meeting ID: 885 2873 5960 Passcode: 716689

Title: Ancient Mesopotamian Astronomical Texts

Speaker: Kevin A. Wilson

Abstract:

This talk will provide an overview of astronomical texts from ancient Babylon and Assyria. It will explore what these texts reveal about what the people in these regions knew about the heavens, Special attention will be given to the Venus Tablets of Amisaduqa, which contain 21 years of Venus observations, and will show how this text allows us to reconstruct aspects of ancient history.

Title: Ancient Mesopotamian Astronomical Texts

Speaker: Kevin A. Wilson

Mini Bio:

Kevin A. Wilson has been an avid astronomer since he received his first telescope at age 12. He has continue his hobby into adulthood, and was most recently the Vice President and Director of the Observatory of the Astronomical Society of Greenbelt, in Maryland. With his move to Knoxville last month, he was pleased to learn about ORION, and start his membership here. Kevin is a graduate of Carson-Newman University, where he double majored in religion and political science. He went on to earn a Master's of Divinity and a Master's of Sacred Theology from Yale Divinity School. He then earned a PhD in Hebrew Bible / Old Testament and Northwest Semitic Philology From the Johns Hopkins University. He has taught college in Klaipėda, Lithuania, North Andover, MA, Sewanee, TN, and Waverly, IA.

Events and Calendars, Sky Maps and Occultations

ORION Last Month

Stellar Spectroscopy for Amateur Astronomers

Our featured speaker for the May 2025 ORION Presentation was new ORION member Kevin A. Wilson. Kevin is a graduate of Carson-Newman University, where he double majored in religion and political science. He went on to earn a Master's of Divinity and a Master's of Sacred Theology from Yale Divinity School, followed by a PhD in Hebrew Bible / Old Testament and Northwest Semitic Philology from the Johns Hopkins University. He has taught college in Klaipėda, Lithuania, North Andover, MA, Sewanee, TN, and Waverly, IA.

Stellar spectroscopy is a field that is rarely explored by amateur astronomers. Until recently, the equipment needed to analyze the spectra of stars was far out of the price range of most amateurs. Recent advances in equipment have removed this barrier, and opened an important new field for amateur astronomers. This lecture introduced people to the field of spectroscopy, explained what we can learn from it, and provided an overview of how one can do spectroscopy as an amateur.

We greatly enjoyed Kevin's presentation, after which he was congratulated by ORION President Don Spong and awarded an appropriate astronomical device to acknowledge our appreciation.

Star, Moon, Comet and Meteorgazing at TAO in 2025

We enthusiastically invite visitors to attend our Public Stargaze events, held at our dark-sky site, the Tamke-Allan Observatory (TAO) near Kingston, Tennessee. These events are intended especially for visitors, so our buildings and facilities will be open, and there will be astronomy talks as well as public skywatching.

In Jan-Jun 2025 we plan to hold fixed-calendar public Stargaze events on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These weekend events are especially appropriate for families. We also hold public special events, such as a “Full Moonrise,” with associated Moon Music, and the occasional comet watch. The annual Perseid Meteor watch in mid-August is especially popular.

The precise dates of many of these events depend on the local weather conditions, and cannot be specified *definitively* long in advance. As an approximate guide, see the TAOCalendar pages following. Once a date is finalized we usually confirm it through the ORION online message site ORION astronomy@groups.io. Likely and unlikely dates for TAO events may be inferred from the weather predictions at TAO by Clear Sky Charts (cleardarksky dot com) and Astrospheric (astrospheric dot com).

Please confirm event dates before proceeding to TAO.

In view of the rather challenging approach road to TAO, “Observatory Way,” first-time visitors should plan to arrive before dark. Driving instructions are given at: <https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/visit.htm>

Some instructions follow, since people may be unfamiliar with procedures for stargazing at a dark-sky site.

ORION members are invited to arrive early with their telescopes and mounts, to prepare for evening observing and to share refreshments. Please bring a red flashlight, or a headband with a red-light option.

Visitors who wish to acquire red lights or red-light headbands for observing may find them at many commercial amateur astronomy sites, such as [https:// www dot high pointscientific dot com](https://www.highpointscientific.com). The “Lepro LE” LED Headlamp, model 3200008, available from Amazon for about \$10 (Aug. 2024) is a personal favorite. This is rechargeable and has separate red and white led buttons, with several brightness settings. A caution: For amateur astronomy, brighter lights are NOT preferred, and WHITE lights are highly discouraged. Please use only red lights while the Stargaze is in progress.

Parking is available on site; on entering TAO **stay to the right**, and *please use the parking area below and right (Southwest) of the TAO buildings and observing area, near the treeline*. And **PLEASE NO HEADLIGHTS ON SITE.**

Visitors are encouraged to interact with ORION astronomers who have set up and may be operating telescopes and other astronomical equipment. We enjoy public discussions, and regard this sharing of information as a primary goal of our organization. Visitors are welcome to coffee and other refreshments.

TAO Public Stargazing: A Note Regarding Scheduling and Access in 2025

In 2025 we will revert to an earlier schedule of having our Public Stargaze nights on every first and third Saturday. Of course this assumes good weather; if the weather is not suitable, a changed schedule will be announced on the group site [ORIONastronomy @ groups.io](mailto:ORIONastronomy@groups.io).

We decided that the previous (2024) schedule of a once-monthly Public Stargaze was insufficient, and having a Moon visible in some phase other than close to New gives our visitors an obvious and interesting object for viewing.

During Daylight Savings Time (mid-March through early November) we plan to hold our Public Stargaze events over the hours 8:00 pm - 11:00 pm. The planned Public Stargaze dates in Apr and Mar of 2025 are 5 Apr, 19 Apr, 3 May and 17 May.

If it is already dark when you arrive, please dim your headlights on the TAO grounds, follow the right branch of the access road, and park to the right of the TAO building, near the treeline.

Note: Parking in or near the elevated flat observing area at the front (East) of the TAO building is reserved for astronomers who are bringing their equipment.

Additional information for visitors may be found on the previous page and following two pages of this issue.

TAO Public Stargazes in May:

Sat 03 & 17 May 2025

Sat 03 May 2025

Sunset	8:29 pm
Civ dusk	8:56 pm
Ast dusk	10:05 pm
Moonrise	12:00 noon
Moonset*	2:51 am
	*04 May
Moon illum.	39%

Crescent Moon during this event.

Cancelled due to weather.

Sat 17 May 2025

Sunset	8:40 pm
Civ dusk	9:09 pm
Ast dusk	10:22 pm
Moonrise	00:40 am
Moonset	10:11 am
Moon illum.	79%

No Moon during this event.

TAO Public Stargazes in June:

Sat 07 & 21 Jun 2025

Sat 07 Jun 2025

Sunset	8:54 pm
Civ dusk	9:24 pm
Ast dusk	10:43 pm
Moonrise	5:50 pm
Moonset*	4:14 am
	*08 Jun
Moon illum.	87%

Bright Gibbous Moon during this event.

Cancelled due to weather.

Sat 21 Jun 2025

Sunset	8:59 pm
Civ dusk	9:30 pm
Ast dusk	10:49 pm
Moonrise	2:51 am
Moonset	5:07 pm
Moon illum.	21%

No Moon during this event.

Finally, after a very long period of rainy and overcast weather, one of our regularly scheduled TAO Public Stargaze dates (1st and 3rd Sat of each month) corresponded to a day of reasonably of reasonably useable weather. The day of Sat 17 May was a beautiful clear blue, with a moderate suggestion of moisture in the sky. The night before had been dominated by continuous storms and tornados in several neighboring states, so the very pleasant weather on Sat 17 May was surprising. After a few discussions on WhatsApp it was clear that this Stargaze would really happen, with people arriving at TAO from 7:00 pm onwards. The nominal recommended time for visitors was moved from 9:00 pm to 8:30 pm for reasons too complicated to review here, so I revised the TAO Calendars in this issue accordingly. Since the Meade LX200 was continuing to have mechanical problems, David Fields had invited George Szdanov to visit TAO on this evening and consider what work might be needed. When I arrived at TAO about 8:15 pm it was clear that we would have a crowd, with about 15 astronomers already present (image 9:10 pm).

Much of the discussion involved recent problems with the Meade LX200 / Celestron CGE, and what could be done to address them. These images of men at work are from 8:53 pm. In the top image, George Szdanov and Ricky Smith are at right, Rob Fowler and Noah Frere at left. A future TAO workday to address Meade problems is planned.

Once the sky darkened a bit we invited out visitors into the TAO building. David Fields gave a presentation on activities at TAO, and Ted Barnes reviewed the current TAO sky and a recent unsuccessful (overcast) occultation attempt involving Mars, entitled “Mars or Bust.” These classroom images are from 9:21 pm.

Four of our astronomers, George Szdanov, Ricky Smith, Don Spong and Kevin Watson, enjoyed setting up on or near our spacious new concrete pads. Although the sky was never free of haze and moisture, it was at least usable, and Don and Kevin were able to capture lovely galaxy images as the evening progressed.

Kevin Watson setting up on the near pad, 8:19 pm.

A view of the “*One TAO Tree*” from the North edge of the near pad at the same time. The Sun at 8:20 pm Eastern is at Alt 2.6° Azi 292.4° , which answers a question I had about the limit of Azimuth visibility from the pad due to the tree. Azi $> 300^\circ$ is the rough limit.

Some of our astronomers (such as moi, I confess) who were somewhat burned out by a long series of overcast and rainy skies at TAO were happy to just sit in camping chairs and admire the (mostly clear) sky through binoculars. In the absence of a Moon, one could pick out faint constellations such as Draco and Corvus for the visitors (I did bring a green laser), and identify two stars for oneself that proved to be in Libra.

Each month, TAO and ORION celebrates an International Friendship Stargaze (IFS) at the International Friendship Bell just west of the Civic Center in the A.K. Bissell Park, Oak Ridge. We choose an honored guest to begin the event. Our first honored and very energetic striker on June 4 was Evie Gibson:

Our first IFS was on Monday evening, Feb.3, 2025. Telescope setup began at 6:30 pm, followed by striking the beautiful International Friendship Bell at 7:00 pm by Bell supporter Pat Postma and visiting kids. We discussed the importance of Astronomy and opportunities for education, and how a monthly Stargaze focused on International Friendship would benefit the community. The date was chosen to provide a first quarter moon.

IFS Stargaze in Oak Ridge (cont.):

Each month offers foci for International Friendship. June 4 was one day after the First Quarter Moon, one day before World Environment Day (a day for global unity and peace with nature), and two days before the Flatwater Tales Storytelling Festival. This year, one of the three tellers was Anne Shimojima. Her family emigrated from Japan in 1909 but were incarcerated by their chosen home country during WWII.

Our second bell striker was Art Allison.

Our first IFS was on Monday evening, Feb.3, 2025. Telescope setup began at 6:30 pm, followed by striking the beautiful International Friendship Bell at 7:00 pm by Bell supporter Pat Postma and visiting kids. We discussed the importance of Astronomy and opportunities for education, and how a monthly Stargaze focused on International Friendship would benefit the community. The date was chosen to provide a first quarter moon.

IFS Stargaze in Oak Ridge (cont.):

Astronomers present for this IFS were Art, Rob, Don, Kevin, David, and Sunny (the Astrodog). Most of us (except Sunny) participated in the spirit of the Stargaze by striking the bell. We enjoyed meeting the other participants and commemorating the evening. The skies were partially cloudy following earlier showers, but we still enjoyed the first quarter moon.

TAO Calendars

Jan-Jun 2025; May & Jun 2025

The principle public events for visitors at TAO are the **Public Stargazes**, held at TAO during 2025 on the 1st and 3rd Saturday of each month. These are listed in the “**Public Fixed Events**” **TAO Calendar** for a six month period, currently Jan-Jun 2025. This appears on the page following.

Additional notable events will be included in monthly “**Special Events**” **TAO Calendars**. These include public events that do not have a fixed date long in advance, such as the **International Friendship Stargaze** in Oak Ridge, and special TAO events such as **Asteroid Occultations, Meteor Showers, Full Moonrises, Lunar (and other) Eclipses, Comet Watches**, and perhaps the occasional musical event.

These “Special Events” calendars for the current and subsequent months appear after the six-month “Public Fixed Events” calendar.

The facilities in the TAO buildings onsite will be open to the public during the “Public Fixed Events,” and will also usually be available when TAO is open to the public for some of the “Special Events.” **Please inquire regarding whether TAO will be open to the public for any “Special Event” you may wish to attend, since some may be restricted.** We will of course always try to accommodate enthusiastic visitors.

We recommend checking a TAO website such as **ORIONastronomy @ groups.io** before visiting, to confirm that listed events will proceed as planned; weather conditions for example may require a cancellation or change of date.

TAO Calendar Public Fixed Events

Jan-Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 04 Jan 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 18 Jan 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Feb 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Feb 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 01 Mar 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	7:00 pm	10:00 pm
Sat 15 Mar 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 05 Apr 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 19 Apr 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:00 pm	11:00 pm
Sat 03 May 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 17 May 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight

These 2025 TAO Public Events are scheduled for fixed calendar days during the weekend, which will hopefully prove convenient for many visitors with families, especially those bringing younger astronomers. Cancellations often take place in Winter and Spring, due to cold or icy conditions, or overcast and rainy skies.

TAOCalendar Special Events

May 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 03 May 2025	<small>cancelled</small> 	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Tue 06 May 2025		Mars occults 9.1 mag TYC 1398-00275-1 midpt <i>ca.</i> 00:45 am EDT	09:00 pm 05 May	01:30 am 06 May
Mon 12 May 2025		Full Moon 02:56 pm Eastern		
Tue 13 May 2025	<small>cancelled</small> 	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	9:00 pm	10:30 pm
Sat 17 May 2025		3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	8:30 pm	11:30 pm
Mon 26 May 2025		New Moon 11:02 pm Eastern		

TAOCalendar Special Events

Jun 2025

date	event	details	start	end
Sat 07 Jun 2025	★	1 st Sat Public Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Wed 04 Jun 2025	★	International Friendship Stargaze (Oak Ridge)	9:00 pm	10:30 pm
Wed 11 Jun 2025	○	Full Moon 03:44 am Eastern		
Sat 21 Jun 2025	★	3 rd Sat Public Stargaze	9:00 pm	midnight
Wed 25 Jun 2025	●	New Moon 06:31 am Eastern		

The evening Sky Map for June 2025 from skymaps.com.

The Evening Sky Map

FREE* EACH MONTH FOR YOU TO EXPLORE, LEARN & ENJOY THE NIGHT SKY

Sky Calendar - June 2025

Follow us on Bluesky
skymaps.com/bluesky/

- 1 Venus at westernmost elongation at 3h UT (46° from Sun, morning sky). Mag. -4.3.
- 1 Moon near Mars at 12h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.3.
- 1 Venus at dichotomy (D-shape) at 22h UT (morning sky).
- 2 Moon near Regulus at 4h UT (evening sky).
- 3 First Quarter Moon at 3:41 UT.
- 6 Moon near Spica at 15h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Antarctica and Tasmania.
- 7 Moon at apogee (farthest from Earth) at 11h UT (distance 405,554km; angular size 29.5').
- 10 Moon near Antares at 12h UT (evening sky). Occultation visible from Australia, New Zealand, Papua New Guinea and eastern Indonesia.
- 11 Full Moon at 7:45 UT.
- 17 Mars 0.7° NNE of Regulus at 18h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.4.
- 18 Last Quarter Moon at 19:20 UT.
- 19 Moon near Saturn at 2h UT (morning sky). Mag. 1.0.
- 21 June solstice at 2:40 UT. The time when the Sun reaches the point farthest north of the celestial equator marking the start of summer in the Northern Hemisphere and winter in the Southern Hemisphere.
- 22 Moon near Venus at 5h UT (morning sky). Mag. -4.2.
- 23 Moon near the Pleiades at 4h UT (morning sky).
- 23 Moon at perigee (closest to Earth) at 4:46 UT (distance 363,178km; angular size 32.9').
- 24 Jupiter at conjunction with the Sun at 15h UT. The largest planet passes into the morning sky.
- 25 New Moon at 10:32 UT. Start of lunation 1268.
- 27 Moon near Mercury at 8h UT (25° from Sun, evening sky). Mag. 0.2.
- 27 Moon near Beehive Cluster (M44) at 20h UT (evening sky).
- 29 Moon near Regulus at 13h UT (evening sky).
- 30 Moon near Mars at 2h UT (evening sky). Mag. 1.5.

More sky events and links at <http://Skymaps.com/skycalendar/>

All times in Universal Time (UT). (USA Eastern Daylight Time - UT - 4 hours.)

Support The Evening Sky Map
Freely shared with sky watchers worldwide since January 2000
Shop: skymaps.com/amazon/ • Donate: skymaps.com/donate/
Recommended Products for Sky Watchers: skymaps.com/store/

NORTHERN HEMISPHERE JUNE 2025

SKY MAP SHOWS HOW THE NIGHT SKY LOOKS

EARLY JUN 11 PM

LATE JUN 10 PM

(+4h from the twilight ending)

SKY MAP DRAWN FOR

A LATITUDE OF 40°

NORTH AND IS

SUITABLE FOR

LATITUDES UP

TO 15° NORTH

OR SOUTH

OF THIS

Symbols

- Galaxy ☁
- Double Star ★
- Variable Star ●
- Diffuse Nebula ☁
- Planetary Nebula □
- Open Star Cluster ○
- Globular Star Cluster ⊙

Star Magnitudes

- -1
- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4

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Note: a nice interactive sky chart from Sky and Telescope may be found at the link <https://skyandtelescope.org/interactive-sky-chart/>

Astrophotography

NGC 4340 is a fascinating double-barred lenticular galaxy, located about 55 Mly distant, in the constellation Coma Berenices, and is a member of the Virgo galaxy cluster. This galaxy stands out due to its unusual internal structure, featuring a small inner bar nestled within a large primary bar. Both bars are composed of stars, and their slight misalignment suggests that they might rotate independently.

A particularly intriguing aspect of this galaxy is the presence of a luminous, gas-poor “fossil” nuclear ring of old stars. Unlike active star-forming rings, this one is made of aged stars and lacks significant gas, indicating that it’s a remnant of a past episode of intense star formation that has since faded. NGC 4340’s complex morphology provides valuable insights into the evolution of barred galaxies.

Art’s 61 min exposure of NGC 4340, captured using his Seestar S50 at TAO, dated 17 May 2025, at 23:48 pm Eastern, is shown on the page following.

NGC 4340

Seestar S50

84°W,35°N/2025-05-17 23:48

NGC 4340

61min

Deep Solar System

- John Barnes

The Editor visited his cousin, ORION member John Barnes, at his residence in suburban Louisville, Ky over the weekend of 24-25 May 2025. Although the local skies are typically only about Bortle 6.5, John has a ZWO Seestar S50 smart telescope that he has nonetheless been putting through its paces from his back porch. Late on the evening of Fri 23 May 2025, since Arcturus was well positioned, the Editor suggested attempting to capture dwarf planet 136108 Haumea, which was also in the constellation Boötes, *albeit* at a challenging v-magnitude of 17.2, and an unsettling distance of 49.1 AU from Earth. After about an hour's exposure Haumea was just visible, as shown below. The field stars are shown with their Gaia g-magnitudes, from Aladin v.12, with one star identified for reference purposes. This image was post processed for brightness, contrast, and to reduce background noise.

Dwarf planet 136108 Haumea
John Barnes, 23 May 2025, Louisville, KY

Deep Solar System (cont.)

- John Barnes

This Aladin image shows the Haumea field on the previous page from the DSS2 deep-sky survey, rotated counterclockwise by about 35° for consistency with that Seestar S50 image. The expected position of Haumea at 11:30 pm Eastern, Fri 23 May 2025 (from JPL Horizons) is shown as a purple plus, and is clearly consistent with the fainter of the two objects visible in the previous image, near the middle of that page.

Dwarf planet 136108 Haumea
JPL Horizons predicted position

Shop Talk

Work continues on the TAO Meade LX-200 telescope.

Stage 1 (OTA) was cleaning of lens surfaces. Thanks, everyone.

Stage 2 was to improve the images by identifying and cleaning up errors (made obvious by examining the Fresnel diffraction patterns of stars – see photo below). Thanks Ted, Rob and David.

Stage 3 (mount hardware upgrades) was identifying and replacing faulty microswitches in the Meade hardware home reference system (Celestron CGX mount).

Stage 4 was cleaning and greasing the gears and some bearings. Thanks, George and David.

Stage 5 (testing) showed that earlier work looked ok, and that there was no loss of RA reference by running the scope from side to side. Thanks, Rob and Kevin.

Stage 6 will be to identify occasional glitches in slewing. Possible causes include incompatible setup of clocks set to EST and EDT in different modules (Celestron mount, control computers using different programs (Celestron, Stellarium, Sky Safari, etc., and GPS); need to replace Li-ion cells in Celestron mount). Rob and David have discussed this. Stage 7 is to explore questions related to electrical noise generated by the switching supply and the effects of the noise on the tracking system (Celestron CGE mount). The approach will be to measure noise and examine if it is associated with a power supply with a low

current rating, or with switching noise harmonics. If a problem for the telescope or nearby system components using Bt or WiFi, we'll install ferrite suppressors. This topic is especially relevant if we want to do radio astronomy from TAO, as we have done several times in the past. More detailed discussion:

On Saturday, May 24, 2025 at 06:36:38 PM EDT, David Fields <fieldsde@aol.com> wrote:

Notes by George and David on 5/24/2025:

The mount is currently served by a (probably inadequate) Celestron 2A power supply. A 5A supply should be ordered -- I will do this. I am delighted that George noticed that we need a power supply rated for a higher current. I will also rig up a current/voltage monitor system to see how close we are to the rated limits with the current supply. We should not just worry just about driving the scope, but we should recognize that the switching power supplies are likely to generate electrical interference when they are overloaded. This may explain some of our glitches during Wi-Fi and bte operation. Before we put the new 5A supply in operation, I will follow George's suggestion and put a few turns of the DC line through a ferrite doughnut to absorb the Rf switching noise.

We serviced the RA electronics section of the CGE mount, resoldering some possible cold solder joints and replacing two micro switches. Also, the RA gear train (worm gear?) was lubed. We exercised the mount and insured that it passes some basic operational tests.

The mount is still in need of receiving lubrication for the Dec worm gear and inspection of the Dec electronics.

Proper operation of the mount depends on proper balancing. We left the system balanced for visual monitoring. It will need to be rebalanced when/if a camera is used.

The new microswitches that we added to the RA mechanics have plastic rollers, which may deform if left in the same position for many hot days. The new switches will probably work for years, but we have no real assurance of their lifetime.

We left the two old microswitches plus one additional new microswitch, in a plastic bag stuffed under a flat plate below the mount. We will add these to the lens box in the dome.

On Sunday, May 25, 2025 at 01:39:56 AM EDT, Djerdj Srdanov <sdjerdj@yahoo.com> wrote:

Thank you David for the detailed notes. Here are a few more details:

After inspecting the PCBs under high magnification, I've found a few solder points that looked as cracked or a bit oxidized. (Images are available.) To be safe, I've re-soldered all of the pins on the 2 PCBs in the RA box.

With that out of the way, the switches were next. Swapping out the switches was straightforward. However, during testing, I noticed that the top switch was bumping into the groove of the lower one. This new problem popped up on multiple threads during my research to find a match for the switches on the mount. I've run across multiple threads dealing with similar problems, as well as dealing with slightly thinner switches. To get the switch off the edge of the groove, we made a small shim and placed it between the 2 switches. Both the shim and the new clearly visible gap are marked in the attached pictures (images available). After adding the shim and adjusting the level of the switches, we got ourselves a nice "click" sound when the switches engage or disengage. We also noticed that the new switches are more firm and require a bit more force to engage. I don't think this will be an issue; perhaps this is how a new switch feels.

Finally, during testing I've observed that the mount behaved slightly different depending on where it pointed. For some reason, this became more obvious when I applied fresh silicon grease to the gears at the end of the motor, as well as to the worm gear. When I checked the power source, I noticed that it is only 2A. For a small mount 2A should be fine, but for something as big as this one, with the big Meade LX-200 mounted on it, I feel this is undersized. I've also observed over the years that if a power supply is pushed to its maximum ratings, it can produce noisy power. I highly recommend we get a 5A power supply. If of a decent quality, it should provide better stability, and produce cleaner power.

This is what I have been using with my EQ-6 - This power supply lets me run the EQ6, the dew heaters and the camera with the cooler on; [https:// www dot amazon dot com/ dp/ B01LX5LRP9](https://www.amazon.com/dp/B01LX5LRP9) .

Ahh, yes. Before I forget. The switches we have now are for normal temperature ranges, with plastic rollers. With the mount being in the dome, the temperature can be pretty high. This could cause the plastics rollers to potentially degrade or deform sooner. Since these are brand new, I don't foresee any issues any time soon, however if we need to replace them, I recommend we use the extended temperature range ones, with metal rollers. I believe a Highly (?) switches ([https:// www. jameco. com/ Jameco/ Products/ ProdDS/ 159599.pdf](https://www.jameco.com/Jameco/Products/ProdDS/159599.pdf)) - the model I believe is SS0505A would match. Another alternative, if not a better one, would be SS5GL02-F from Omron ([https:// omronfs. omron. com/ en_US/ ecb/ products/p df/ en-ss.pdf](https://omronfs.omron.com/en_US/ecb/products/pdf/en-ss.pdf) - the 02 is for the steel roller).

All in all, I'm pretty happy with the work done. Please keep me posted how the mount behaves.

Best regards,
George

n.b. The Editor made some minor, largely grammatical changes in the “Shop Talk” article where they appeared appropriate. The occasional remaining uncertainties are indicated by question marks.

External Event

We would like to invite you and your club members to attend the upcoming annual four-day Green Bank Star Quest 20, being held June 25 through June 28, 2025. It is the largest star party in the nation that combines both optical and radio astronomy. Held at the Green Bank Observatory, located in Green Bank, West Virginia, the rural location provides the dark skies so envied by many other astronomers.

Green Bank Observatory graciously allows us to hold this star party at their facility, where the infrastructure allows events and lectures to continue, even if there is inclement weather. Large campsites are available in the observing field with nearby hot showers. Bunkhouses are also available for a small fee of \$15 per night to help accommodate astronomers. Anyone paying for the full event for four days may choose to arrive on Tuesday. The camping field and bunkhouse will be available, but the bunkhouse is \$15 for each night you stay, including Tuesday night, if you choose to arrive early.

Each year we choose to have the highest quality speakers available, covering a wide variety of topics that would interest both optical and radio astronomers. Additional information is available at this link: <https://greenbankstarquest.org> .

There will be a 10% group discount for groups of ten or more (**pre-paid and non-refundable, unless the event would get cancelled again due to circumstances out of our control**). **The discount is off of the registration fee only, and does not include bunkhouse, RV sites, or any other special fees.**

Green Bank Observatory has informed us that only service dogs currently in service are allowed on the Observatory. No other animals, including emotional support dogs, will be allowed at or near the visitor center, or anywhere else on the Green Bank campus. Service dogs must remain with their humans at all times, due to liability issues.

For anyone who is interested in attending, a registration form is available on our website. The option to use PayPal is also available on our website: <https://greenbankstarquest.org> .

Our club can be contacted by mail: Central Appalachian Astronomy Club, P.O. Box 211, Grafton, WV 26354-0211, or via the club's website: <https://caacwv.com/contact.htm> , or you can contact the coordinator of the event, our club's vice president, John Taylor, at (304) 265-5514.

Sincerely,

Central Appalachian Astronomy Club, WV

Green Bank Star Quest 20 (cont.)

REGISTRATION FORM GREEN BANK STAR QUEST 20, June 25 -28, 2025

Registration fee is **Per Person** and includes: Attendance to all events at the Visitor Center (including activities for children) and a campsite. (Children 18 and under admitted free but must be accompanied by at least one registered adult). Free bath house facilities for both genders, commemorative registration tag with lanyard. The observing field camp sites are non-electric sites. Electric for battery charging only, is available at the white barn in the camping area. **NO GENERATORS:** They cause Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) with the Radio Telescopes. Please note that a limited number of registrations are available, and it is necessary for us to restrict registration for this event to a **2-day minimum** registration. Green Bank Star Quest has a **"No refund"** policy after June 10, 2025. GBO or CAAC will not be responsible for accidents or stolen items. **Only ADA certified dogs allowed at Star Quest.**

This Mail-In Event Registration form must be postmarked on or before June 8, 2025:		Amount
4 Days	Reg. rate \$125 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
3 Days	Reg. rate \$100 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
2 Days	Reg. rate \$80 Per adult - x _____ (# of adults) = _____	
Registration Sub Total =		_____

Day Pass* \$ 35 x _____ Per adult) = _____
 *Day Pass is for all events at the Visitor Center only. NO overnight camping or use of shower facilities.

Bunkhouse is an extra \$15 per night per person and there are a limited number of spaces available
 Number of Males _____ x \$15 per night = _____ x _____ (No. of nights) = _____
 Number of Females _____ x \$15 per night = _____ x _____ (No. of nights) = _____

Bunkhouse is separated by gender, and is limited to only 30 males, and 30 females. You must provide your own pillow, and sleeping bag. The Bunkhouse is provided on a first-come first-serve basis. You must specify your needs at the time of registration. The Bunkhouse is \$15.00 per person per night, with a minimum of a 2 nights.

RV SITE "For Special Needs ONLY!" RV Length _____ Fee \$30 = _____

The RV Site is LIMITED TO SPECIAL NEEDS; you must notify us in advance of those needs. The RV site is closer to shower facilities and on a paved lot. Electrical hook ups are also limited and **MAY NOT** be available, **NO GENERATORS:** They cause Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) with the Radio Telescopes

Please make your Check or Money Order payable to Green Bank Star Quest- **Total Amount Enclosed:** = _____

Mail this entire form to: **GREEN BANK STAR QUEST, PO BOX 211, GRAFTON, WV 26354-0211**

(Please Print)

Names of Registrants: _____

Address: _____

City, State, Zip: _____

Phone Number and Email Address: _____

*Number and ages of Children 18 and Under attending with you _____

For more information or assistance call John Taylor 304-265-5514 or Jim King (304) 694-0277

Meal Plan: Homestyle Breakfast, and/or Dinner will be offered by GBO. Tickets can be purchased at the Starlight Café. GBO will post a menu around noon on Wednesday. Lunch and snacks available at the Starlight Café.

Free Optional Activity that is included in your registration: The Green Bank Observatory (GBO) will be offering specialized classes and the use of the 40-foot radio telescope, free to a limited number of Star Quest registrants. **Class size and number of classes are limited!** This activity is provided on a first-come first-serve basis. If you are interested: Please sign up at the registration desk when you arrive. You will receive classroom instruction on the objects to be observed. Then at an appointed time, your group will do observing with the 40-foot radio telescope. GBO will work with teams of ten, some will be during the daytime hours and some will be at night. Each team will actually be able to collect real data that can be analyzed. There is no charge to participants for this program. Revision 082824

If you have comments or specials needs , please let us know:

Appendices

Astronomy

- tb

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate.
Exact numerical relationships are indicated as such.

1 ly = 1 ly (Julian) = *exactly* 9 460 730 472 580. 8 km = 63 241. 077 084 ... AU
c = speed of light = *exactly* 299 792 458 m/s = *exactly* ☺ 1 ly/yr.
1 AU = *exactly* 149 597 870. 7 km
1 parsec (pc) = 3. 261 598 ... light years (ly)
1 yr (Julian) = *exactly* 365.25 d = *exactly* 31 557 600 s
1 d = *exactly* 86 400 s

distance to α Cen A = 1.346(2) pc = 4.390(8) ly
distance to the center of the galaxy ~ 8 kpc ~ 25 kly (considerable uncertainty)

1 nm = 1 nanometer = 10^{-9} m *exactly*
 H_{α} wavelength = 656.2 nm

+ 0.5 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{1/5}$ x fainter =	1. 584 893 ... x fainter
+ 1 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{2/5}$ x fainter =	2. 511 886 ... x fainter
+ 2 change in magnitude	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{4/5}$ x fainter =	6. 309 ... x fainter
+ 2.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^1 x fainter =	10 x fainter
+ 3 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{6/5}$ x fainter =	15. 848 ... x fainter
+ 4 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{8/5}$ x fainter =	39. 810 ... x fainter
+ 5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^2 x fainter =	100 x fainter
+ 6 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{12/5}$ x fainter =	251. 188 ... x fainter
+ 7.5 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^3 x fainter =	1000 x fainter
+ 8 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> $10^{16/5}$ x fainter =	1584. 893 ... x fainter
+ 10 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^4 x fainter =	10 000 x fainter
+ 20 change in mag	= <i>exactly</i> 10^8 x fainter =	100 000 000 x fainter

Brightness is proportional to $1 / \text{distance}^2$

10 x more distant = *exactly* 10^2 x fainter = + 5 change in magnitude
 10^2 x more distant = *exactly* 10^4 x fainter = + 10 change in mag
 10^3 x more distant = *exactly* 10^6 x fainter = + 15 change in mag

Absolute magnitude M_{abs} is the brightness as seen from a distance of 10 pc
 M_{abs} (our sun) = 4.83

17th mag is about 1 optical photon / cm^2 s (Barnes's rule ☺)

Astronomy (cont.)

Some numbers are quoted to several-digit accuracy where appropriate. *Exact* numerical relationships are indicated as such.

R.A. = RA = Right Ascension = the angle ϕ around the celestial polar axis, usually quoted in hours, minutes, and seconds (*h m s*); analogous to longitude.

Dec = Declination = the angle θ above the celestial equator, usually quoted in degrees, minutes, and seconds ($^{\circ} \ ' \ ''$); analogous to latitude.

The RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles, together with a reference epoch such as J2000.0, specify an object's direction in the sky.

A unit length vector ("unit vector") $\boldsymbol{\eta}$ pointing towards an object in the sky ("on the celestial sphere") in terms of RA (ϕ) and Dec (θ) angles is given by

$$\boldsymbol{\eta} = \cos(\theta) \cos(\phi) \mathbf{x} + \cos(\theta) \sin(\phi) \mathbf{y} + \sin(\theta) \mathbf{z} = C(c \mathbf{x} + s \mathbf{y}) + S \mathbf{z}$$

The arc angle Θ_{12} between any two directions in the sky $\boldsymbol{\eta}_1$ and $\boldsymbol{\eta}_2$ (or any two stars) using the dot product formula and some obvious abbreviations, satisfies

$$\cos(\Theta_{12}) = \sin(\theta_1)\sin(\theta_2) + \cos(\theta_1)\cos(\theta_2)\cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2) = S_1 S_2 + C_1 C_2 c_{1-2}$$

$$1 \text{ degree} = \pi/180 \text{ radians} = 1.745 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcmin} = \pi/10800 \text{ radians} = 2.909 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ arcsec} = 1 \text{ asec} = \pi/648000 \text{ radians} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} = 10^{-3} \text{ asec} = 4.848 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ radians}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ km} = 4.848 \text{ mm}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ AU} = 725.3 \text{ km}$$

$$1 \text{ asec} @ 1 \text{ pc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

$$1 \text{ mas} @ 1 \text{ kpc} = 1.0000 \text{ AU}$$

JD = Julian Date (Astronomer's calendar) = a simple count of days starting at noon UT on Monday 1 Jan 4713 BC. That date and time was the start of Julian Day 0. The current JD can be inferred from the value on the cover of the Trapezium.

The 80 Brightest Stars

The 80 brightest stars (c/o Wikipedia), and their distances from Earth in light years, the first 40 with errors (from Gaia data).

1	Sirius	8.709	0.005	41	Menkalinan	81.1
2	Canopus	309.	16.	42	Atria	390.6
3	alpha Centauri A	4.395	0.008	43	Alhena	109.3
4	Arcturus	36.7	0.2	44	Peacock	178.8
5	Vega	25.04	0.07	45	Alsephina	80.6
6	Capella	42.81	0.26	46	Mirzam	492.7
7	Rigel	863.	78.	47	Polaris	432.6
8	Procyon	11.46	0.05	48	Alphard	177.3
9	Archenar	139.4	3.4	49	Hamal	65.8
10	Betelgeuse	498.	63.	50	Diphda	96.3
11	beta Centauri	392.	24.	51	Mizar	97.8
12	Altair	16.73	0.05	52	Nunki	227.8
13	alpha Crucis	322.	16.	53	Menkent	58.8
14	Aldebaran	66.64	1.05	54	Alpheratz	97.0
15	Antares	554.	94.	55	Mirach	197.4
16	Spica	250.	13.	56	Rasalhague	48.6
17	Pollux	33.78	0.09	57	Algieba	130.1
18	Fomalhaut	25.13	0.09	58	Kochab	130.9
19	Deneb	1410	200	59	Saiph	647.1
20	Mimosa	279.	23.	60	Denebola	35.9
21	Regulus	79.30	0.67	61	Algol	94.0
22	Adhara	405.	7.0	62	Tiaki	177.0
23	Castor	50.68	0.032	63	Muhlifain	130.2
24	Shaula	571.2	7.5	64	Aspidiske	765.6
25	Gacrux	88.56	0.43	65	Suhail	544.5
26	Bellatrix	252.4	10.2	66	Alphecca	75.0
27	Elnath	133.9	1.9	67	Mintaka	692.5
28	Miaplacidus	113.2	0.43	68	Sadr	1832.3
29	Alnilam	1980	540	69	Eltanin	154.3
30	Regor	1120	110	70	Schedar	228.2
31	Alnair	101.0	0.66	71	Naos	1083.6
32	Alnitak	736.	106.	72	Almach	393.0
33	Alioth	82.55	0.42	73	Caph	54.7
34	Dubhe	122.9	2.2	74	Izar	235.8
35	Mirfak	506.	13.	75	alpha Lupi	464.6
36	Wezen	1610	300	76	epsilon Centauri	427.5
37	Sargas	300.	41.	77	Dschubba	491.2
38	Kaus Australis	143.3	1.5	78	Larawag	63.7
39	Avior	605.	47.	79	eta Centauri	305.7
40	Alkaid	103.9	0.79	80	Merak	79.7

Notable Star-Pair Angles

Notable star pairs (from the set of the 80 brightest stars listed above) that are close to a multiple of 5° separation. The angles are in degrees.

		<u>Θ</u>	<u>Δθ</u>	<u>defect (%)</u>
Schedar	Caph	5	-0.085	1.7
Betelgeuse	Alnitak	10	0.017	0.17
Capella	Castor	30	-0.023	0.077
Procyon	Mirzam	30	-0.094	0.31
Elnath	Alnilam	30	-0.096	0.32
Alpheratz	Caph	30	0.060	0.20
Aldebaran	Pollux	45	0.013	0.029
Betelgeuse	Algol	50	-0.033	0.066
Alnitak	Naos	50	-0.049	0.098
Pollux	Alioth	60	0.065	0.11
Gacrux	Alphard	60	-0.001	0.002
Regulus	Bellatrix	70	-0.030	0.043
Sirius	Mirfak	80	-0.094	0.12
alpha_Centauri	Regulus	90	0.057	0.063
Vega	Denebola	90	-0.065	0.072
Fomalhaut	Caph	90	0.006	0.007
Deneb	Alnilam	120	0.059	0.049
Menkent	Mintaka	120	0.000	0.000
Sirius	Alphecca	135	-0.089	0.066
Aldebaran	Antares	170	-0.021	0.012

Exeunt

*Antenna searches
Retriever's nose in the wind
Aether's far secrets.*

アンテナや 秘密かぎとる犬の鼻

Haiku

Corporal Shaftoe,
Cryptonomicon
by Neal Stephenson

ORION and TAO (and Obed) General Information (links)

May be found at the following URLs:

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Tamke-Allan_Observatory

<http://www.orioninc.org/>

<https://orionastronomy.wordpress.com>

<https://www.facebook.com/ORIONAstronomyTN/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/454645124557215>

<https://www.facebook.com/pages/Tamke-Allan%20Observatory/120477734665841>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/?349-Tamke-Allan-Observatory>

<https://www.roanestate.edu/pages/obs/index.htm>

<https://twitter.com/TAOremote>

ORIONastronomy@groups.io

Where is TAO?

334 Caney Creek Rd, Rockwood, TN 37854

N 35° 49' 57", W 84° 37' 04"; Alt. 324 m

Where is Obed?

Lilly Bluff Overlook

N 36° 06' 09", W 84° 43' 17"; Alt. 402 m

Nemo Bridge (on the bridge, E bank of Emory River)

N 36° 04' 07", W 84° 39' 43"; Alt. 268 m

Trapezium back issues online:

Vol. 49, Issue 4; Fri 15 Apr 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8219253
Vol. 49, Issue 5; Fri 12 May 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8216818
Vol. 49, Issue 6; Fri 16 Jun 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8030659
Vol. 49, Issue 7; Fri 14 Jul 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8140396
Vol. 49, Issue 8; Fri 18 Aug 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8251302
Vol. 49, Issue 9; Fri 15 Sep 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8336647
Vol. 49, Issue 10; Fri 13 Oct 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8433081
Vol. 49, Issue 11; Fri 17 Nov 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10138151
Vol. 49, Issue 12; Fri 15 Dec 2023:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10382618
Vol. 50, Issue 01; Fri 12 Jan 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10483283
Vol. 50, Issue 02; Fri 16 Feb 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10672625
Vol. 50, Issue 03; Fri 15 Mar 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10822600
Vol. 50, Issue 04; Fri 12 Apr 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10967036
Vol. 50, Issue 05; Fri 10 May 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11176951
Vol. 50, Issue 06; Fri 14 Jun 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11646971
Vol. 50, Issue 07, Fri 12 Jul 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735071
Vol. 50, Issue 08, Fri 16 Aug 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13333599
Vol. 50, Issue 09, Fri 13 Sep 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13742825
Vol. 50, Issue 10, Fri 11 Oct 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13921735
Vol. 50, Issue 11, Fri 15 Nov 2024:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14171218
Vol. 50, Issue 12, Fri 13 Dec 2024:	https://zenodo.org/records/14394899
Vol. 51, Issue 01, Fri 10 Jan 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14630165
Vol. 51, Issue 02, Fri 14 Feb 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/14873015
Vol. 51, Issue 03, Fri 14 Mar 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15015954
Vol. 51, Issue 04, Fri 11 Apr 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15200349
Vol. 51, Issue 05, Fri 16 May 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15443035
Vol. 51, Issue 06, Fri 13 Jun 2025:	https://zenodo.org/records/15660329

A generic link that lists Trapezium pdf issues (and other ORION documents) starting with the most recent, which does not require a specific zenodo document number, follows:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/rigel/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Fin du journal

Two visitors enjoying an almost clear evening during the TAO Public Stargaze of Sat 17 May, while astronomers set up for the evening's viewing on the two new pads. Image captured 9:10 pm Eastern.